

Dosing extracellular vesicles

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 29 March 2021

Revised 19 July 2021

Accepted 30 August 2021

Available online 2 September 2021

Keywords:

Exosome
Drug delivery
EV therapeutics
Engineered EVs
Therapeutic dosing

ABSTRACT

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are natural nanoparticles containing biologically active molecules. They are important mediators of intercellular communication and can be exploited therapeutically by various bio-engineering approaches. To accurately determine the therapeutic potential of EVs in pre-clinical and clinical settings, dependable dosing strategies are of utmost importance. However, the field suffers from inconsistencies comprising all areas of EV production and characterisation. Therefore, a standardised and well-defined process in EV quantification, key to reliable therapeutic EV dosing, remains to be established. Here, we examined 64 pre-clinical studies for EV-based therapeutics with respect to their applied EV dosing strategies. We identified variations in effective dosing strategies irrespective of the applied EV purification method and cell source. Moreover, we found dose discrepancies depending on the disease model, where EV doses were selected without accounting for published EV pharmacokinetics or biodistribution patterns. We therefore propose to focus on qualitative aspects when dosing EV-based therapeutics, such as the potency of the therapeutic cargo entity. This will ensure batch-to-batch reliability and enhance reproducibility between applications. Furthermore, it will allow for the successful benchmarking of EV-based therapeutics compared to other nanoparticle drug delivery systems, such as viral vector-based or lipid-based nanoparticle approaches.

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Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. EV isolation	2
3. EV quantification	3
4. EV dosing in pre-clinical and clinical studies	3
5. Summary	9
Declaration of Competing Interest	9
Acknowledgements	9
References	9

1. Introduction

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are membranous natural nanoparticles released by all cell types and present in all biological fluids. Generally, EVs are broadly divided into three major subtypes -

microvesicles (MVs), exosomes, and apoptotic bodies – according to their biogenesis pathway, size, and content, as well as biological function [1,2]. In addition to this classification, it is also getting increasingly evident that various sub-populations of vesicles exist, especially various types of exosomes [3]. As nature's very own nanoparticles, EVs inherently benefit from immune tolerance, stability in circulation systems as well as the ability to cross biological barriers to reach distant organs such as the brain [2,4]. EVs contain

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biologically active molecules as cargo from their producer cell [1,5]. The horizontal transfer of these macromolecules renders EVs important mediators of intercellular communication and can be exploited therapeutically [1,2,5]. Using EVs as nanocarriers further provides the possibility to specifically bioengineer them to carry therapeutic cargo molecules. The techniques for cargo loading into EVs can be broadly divided into two basic approaches: exogenous and endogenous loading. Exogenous loading usually encompasses the incorporation of cargo into, or onto, pre-isolated EVs by various methods, including co-incubation, sonication, and electroporation [2,6,7]. For endogenous loading, the parental cells are genetically engineered to overexpress a desired RNA or protein, with or without specific modifications, which is then incorporated into the secreted vesicles during EV biogenesis [2,6,8,9].

To accurately determine the therapeutic potential of engineered EVs, well-designed *in vivo* applications are indispensable. For correct measures of therapeutic efficacy, dynamics, and kinetics of EV-borne cargo, accurate and dependable dosing strategies are of utmost importance. However, to date, the field of therapeutic EV research suffers from inconsistencies comprising all areas of EV production, including methods for EV isolation, quantification, and characterisation [10]. A standardised, streamlined, and well-defined process in EV manufacturing is key to reliable therapeutic EV dosing in pre-clinical and clinical settings.

This review aims to briefly list currently used methods in EV dosing, discuss their underlying quantification techniques and identify possible pitfalls associated with these approaches. Furthermore, we examine published pre-clinical studies for EV-based therapeutics with respect to their applied EV dosing strategies to identify effective dose-ranges for different therapeutic EV cargo entities. A favourable dosing strategy is based on an EV quantification method that is firstly tailored to the EV engineering strategy, the parental cell type and isolation method, and secondly tailored for the experimental *in vivo* application and the underlying scientific question. In 2017 an international consortium published a meta-analysis of more than 1000 studies from various areas in EV research, revealing a widespread heterogeneity in EV isolation methods [10]. They reported 190 distinctive isolation methods and 1,038 unique protocols to retrieve EVs from biofluids, along with insufficient documentation of main experimental parameters. This study powerfully demonstrated that despite the abundance of available methods for EV isolation, quantification, and characterisation, universally applicable and standardised protocols remain elusive. Thus, when an EV dosing strategy for *in vivo* application is designed, careful consideration and mindfulness about the experimental parameters and EV characteristics are necessary.

2. EV isolation

Generally, EVs are isolated based on their density, size, biological composition, surface biomarkers, or affinity to specific molecules. Low-speed differential centrifugation is very commonly combined with microfiltration steps (see below) to clear biological fluids or cell culture supernatants from cells, cell debris, and other large particles. This pre-clearance procedure is usually followed by one or more concentration steps using ultracentrifugation at 100,000–200,000g [11,12]. For increased EV purity, a 30–60% sucrose cushion or iodixanol can be used in the final ultracentrifugation step for the removal of vesicle-free proteins or protein-RNA aggregates [11,13,14]. As the sedimentation efficiency of EVs and the buoyancy depend on the viscosity of the sample, the applied parameters should be based on the EV source as well as the downstream application [11]. Furthermore, EV integrity can be altered or compromised due to the shear force generated during the

centrifugation process [15,16]. Another technique employing low-speed centrifugation is the direct EV precipitation by addition of polyethylene glycol [17], protamine [18], sodium acetate [19], or organic solvent (Protein Organic Solvent Precipitation (PROSPR) technique) [20], usually commercially available as proprietary reagents. These compounds enforce EV aggregation by changing their solubility or surface charge. Precipitated EVs are heterogeneous and usually contaminated by co-precipitated large protein complexes [17,20]. This is a critical aspect commonly neglected. A range of high-impact studies have used these EV enrichment kits and concluded that EVs drive various biological processes. Although the majority of observed effects likely can be attributed to EVs, it is crucial to be aware that some effects can be imparted by contaminating proteins or other co-precipitated macromolecules.

Popular methods for EV isolation based on size are micro- and ultrafiltration and size exclusion chromatography (SEC). Microfiltration typically follows low-speed centrifugation and encompasses the use of filters with pore diameters of 0.8, 0.45, 0.22, and 0.1 μm . They retain particles with diameters over 800, 450, 220, and 100 nm, respectively ($\pm 20\%$), thus enriching the suspension for particles of specified sizes [21]. For further vesicle concentration, pre-cleared samples are subjected to ultrafiltration devices with a low molecular weight cut-off (MWCO), ranging from 10 to 1000 kDa [22,23]. A well-established ultrafiltration method to process large volumes of biological fluids or cell culture supernatant is tangential flow filtration (TFF) using hollow fiber filter devices [24–26]. Depending on the cut-off values, micro- and ultrafiltration approaches yield relatively pure and intact vesicle preparations with defined size distribution and reduced low-molecular-weight contaminants [24]. They exclude, however, a substantial fraction of vesicles that might contribute to a biological function. In SEC, samples pass through chromatography columns with a defined pore size, where large particles elute earlier than small particles [16,26,27]. EVs isolated by SEC are heterogeneous in size and purified with less than 5% cellular protein contamination [28].

Affinity-based EV purification allows for the separation of EV subpopulations based on the capture of EV surface markers. To date, a wide range of EV markers have been identified, and a plethora of capture molecules for affinity purification is commercially available. Examples include anti-MHC antigen antibodies [29], anti-heat shock protein antibodies [30], anti-CD9, -CD63, -CD81 antibodies [31], annexin-V, which binds to phosphatidylserine on the EV membrane [32], heparin [33], and lectins, which bind to carbohydrate motifs of glycolipid, glycoproteins, and proteoglycans [34–36]. Capture molecules can either be applied directly or immobilised on magnetic beads to serve as precipitants [29–31] or bound to the stationary phase in affinity chromatography [37]. The advantage of affinity based EV purification is the isolation of pure and homogenous EV yields [38]. However, the scalability of this method is low and novel strategies to retrieve the EVs from the affinity resin without affecting the integrity are needed. Furthermore, by design, the affinity chromatography eliminates potentially biologically relevant EV subpopulations lacking the target capture molecule. Therefore, future efforts on identifying therapeutically relevant EV subpopulations may consolidate the feasibility of this method.

A particularly intriguing approach for an affinity-based EV isolation technique is EV sorting based on flow cytometry. As EVs are submicron-sized vesicles with their vast majority smaller than 200 μm in diameter, flow cytometric EV analysis and sorting is technologically extremely challenging. Furthermore, reliable EV measurement signals are close to detection limits of even high-resolution flow cytometers, diffuse light scattering noise derived from systemic components, such as buffers, optics, and electronics, substantially overlap with specific EV signals [152,153]. During the

last decade, a substantial amount of work in the field was dedicated to the establishment of flow cytometry approaches for sub-micron sized particles. To enable their reliable distinction from systemic noise, conventional flow cytometers, both jet-in-air systems and cuvette-based systems, were modified with high-resolution technological equipment. These include, but are by far not limited to, high-performance forward and side scatter detectors, optimized channel threshold settings, sheath flow speed and pressure optimizations, application of high-resolution objective lenses, and improved laser beam dimension settings for sub-micron single particle detection. Aside from the technological challenges, EV flow cytometry requires tremendous theoretical and practical user expertise and is thus not easily established [56,153–156].

EV flow cytometry aims at the detection of specific epitopes and, therefore, EV sorting based on flow cytometry enriches EV populations carrying specific surface markers. However, currently this approach produces preparative quantities suitable for small-scale downstream functional assays or analysis only and is not developed yet for large-scale EV preparations [154–156]. Still, the successful establishment of EV flow cytometry and emerging sorting technologies of intact vesicles belong to the most important achievements in the field yet and will prove invaluable in the future.

3. EV quantification

EVs have a characteristic structure and contain proteins, lipids, nucleic acids, and other biomolecules as cargo. The measurement of each of these components can be used as a surrogate quantification for EVs. However, none of these parameters is perfectly correlated with the actual EV number [39,40]. EVs are quantified by either one or a combination of the following measures: particle number, total protein amount, total lipid abundance, total RNA, or the presence of specific molecules.

Particle counts can be assessed by light scattering technologies, such as nanoparticle tracking analysis (NTA) [41], by standard flow cytometry for larger EVs [42–45] or high resolution or image-based flow cytometry for smaller EVs [46–57], by resistive pulse sensing (RPS) for a wide range of sizes, depending on pore size [58], by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM) [59], or by a platform combining surface plasmon resonance (SPR) with AFM [60]. Precise quantitation of particle numbers is only possible within a certain particle concentration and size range, as the accuracy of the applied method relies strongly on the platform and the sample. Furthermore, particle counting technologies may have a bias towards specific particle size ranges due to diminished sensitivity for smaller particles or the inability to account for polydispersity as reported for dynamic light scattering (DLS) [61–63].

Total protein amount of EV preparations can be determined by multiple standard colorimetric assays (Bradford or micro-bicinchoninic acid (BCA)) or fluorometric assays, or by global protein stain on SDS-PAGE. Overestimation of vesicle quantification is a major pitfall of this method due to the presence of co-isolated protein contaminants, mainly when less specific methods of EV isolation were used [40].

Total lipid quantification can be realised by sulfophosphovanillin assay [64], by using fluorescent phospholipid dyes incorporated into EV lipid bilayers, such as DiR [65], or by total reflection Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy [66]. However, these techniques either require specialised equipment or maybe insufficiently sensitive for small amounts of EVs, while they also may not detect all EVs due to specificities in the different lipid compositions.

Quantification of total RNA can be achieved by global RNA assays, including profiles obtained by capillary electrophoresis instruments [67]. However, while RNA measurements are important parameters during EV characterisation, they are neither recommended for proper EV quantification nor for the assessment of EV purity [40]. RNA quantification from EVs can be highly skewed, as non-vesicular extracellular RNAs are very abundant in EV preparations, particularly as part of ribonucleoproteins [68–70], and other particles such as exomeres [71] and lipoproteins [72].

Methods to detect specific molecules are another measure to quantify EVs. They include ELISA [73], bead-based flow cytometry [74–76], aptamer- and carbon nanotube-based colorimetric assays [77], or SPR on surfaces such as antibody-coated nanorods [60,78,79]. The target molecules are usually the tetraspanins CD9, CD63, and/or CD81, but occasionally tumor-specific proteins or other molecules such as specific lipids [80]. These methods are a valuable addition to the above-mentioned quantification methods as they provide a deeper insight into physical EV characteristics and thus can be used to estimate the amount of EVs containing a particular component.

Due to the varying degree in EV population heterogeneity and purity introduced by the choice of isolation method, the total amount of EVs cannot be quantified in an unbiased manner using any one of the abovementioned EV quantification methods. With the high potential and increasing interest in using EVs as a tool for tissue-specific delivery of biotherapeutics such as small RNA, siRNA, miRNA, mRNA, therapeutic proteins, and small molecule compounds, new tools for EV quantification and bioprocessing are in high demand for the successful clinical implementation of EV-based therapeutics. Despite significant development in the past decade, the field has faced significant limitations concerning manufacturing, purification, and characterisation [81,82]. Strong variations in every step from purification to characterisation significantly contribute to the relative lack of robustness in the application of EV-based therapeutics, as suggested by the meta-analysis below.

4. EV dosing in pre-clinical and clinical studies

To accurately determine the potential of EVs as therapeutics, well-designed *in vivo* applications are indispensable. However, general guidelines for EV dosing *in vivo*, taking pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics into account, are not established yet. Here, we performed a meta-analysis of the published studies on *in vivo* applications of EV-based therapeutics to determine an effective dose for future efforts. To get a broader overview of EV dosing strategies, we selected 64 different pre-clinical studies across numerous disease areas utilising native or engineered EVs as a therapeutic intervention. We included studies which performed (1) in-depth characterisation of EVs, (2) detailed analysis of the disease-associated biomarker to show the therapeutic effect and were (3) the first study where specific cell source derived EVs or engineered EVs were used as a therapeutic intervention for the described disease. We compared studies with respect to the target disease, route of administration, amount of EVs injected, frequency of dosing, EV cell source and culturing conditions, purification method, and whether native or engineered EVs were used for treatment. For a better comparison of EV dosing strategies, we segregated the data set into four different groups based upon target diseases type: cardiovascular (Table 1), neurological (Table 2), malignancies (Table 3), and systemic diseases (Table 4).

The majority of the analysed studies quantified the applied *in vivo* doses of EVs based on the total protein amount (39 out of 64 studies) followed by particle numbers using RPS or NTA as a basis of EV dose quantification in 14 pre-clinical studies. We

Table 1
Summary of dosing strategy of selected preclinical studies targeting cardiovascular diseases using EV-based therapeutics.

Disease model	Animal	Route of injection	Dosing scheme	Purification	Therapeutic cargo	Cell source	Ref.
M.I	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 0.4 µg EV protein in saline immediately post disease induction (p.d.i)	SEC	Native	hESC derived MSC (SF)	[25]
M.I	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 0.1 µg-0.4 µg EV protein in saline, 5 min before reperfusion	SEC	Native	hESC derived MSC (SF)	[104]
M.I	Rat	I.M.C	1 injection of 300 µg EV protein in PBS, 60 min p.d.i	Exoquick	Native	hCPC (SF)	[105]
M.I	Rat	I.M.C	1 injection of 80 µg EV protein in APOP buffer immediately p.d.i	UC	Native	hBM-MS (Hypoxia + SF)	[106]
M.I	Pig	I.C	1 injection of 7.5 mg EV protein in PBS immediately p.d.i	UC	Native	Cardiac cells derived from hiPSCs (EV depleted serum)	[107]
M.I	Pig	I.V	14 injections of 1 mg EV protein, twice daily for 7 days p.d.i	UF	Native	hESC derived MSC (SF)	[108]
M.I	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 10 µg EV protein in PBS immediately p.d.i	Exoquick	Native	mDC (SF)	[109]
M.I	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 2×10^{10} particles in PBS immediately p.d.i	UC	Native	rBM-MS overexpressing HIF-1alpha (EV depleted serum)	[110]
M.I	Pig	I.C and I.M.C	I.C administration of 15 mg EV protein (3.3×10^{12} particles) or I.M.C administration of 7.5 mg EV protein (1.65×10^{12} particles) in IMDM, 30 min p.d.i. For chronic MI model I.M.C administration of 7.5 mg EV protein (1.65×10^{12} particles) in IMDM, 4 weeks p.d.i	PEG precipitation	Native	hCardiosphere derived cells (SF)	[111]
M.I	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 4×10^9 particles/50 µg EV protein in PBS immediately p.d.i	Total exosome isolation kit	Endogenously engineered with Lamp2B IMTP	mBM-MS (EV depleted serum)	[112]
M.I	Mouse	I.V	5 injection of 200 µg EV protein in PBS, at 0 h, 4 hrs, 24 hrs, 48 hrs and 7 days p.d.i	UC	Exogenously engineered with IMTP targeting peptide	mBM-MS (Hypoxia + EV depleted serum)	[113]
M.I	Rat	I.V	1 injection of 6.0×10^9 particles in PBS at 4 hrs p.d.i	UF	Exogenously engineered with cardiac homing peptide	hCardiosphere derived cells (SF)	[114]
M.I	Mouse	I.M.C	1 injection of 100 µg EV protein in PBS immediately p.d.i	Exoquick	Exogenously engineered with miR-21 inhibitor or Mimic using Exofect reagent.	hPBMC	[115]

Myocardial Infarction (M.I); Intravenous (I.V); Intramyocardial (I.M.C); Intracoronary (I.C); Ultra-centrifugation (UC); Ultrafiltration (UF); Ischemic myocardium-targeting peptide(IMTP); Human (h); Rat (r); Mouse (m); Serum Free (SF); Bone Marrow (BM); Embryonic Stem Cells (ESC)

observed large inconsistencies in the effective doses ranging from 0.001 to 100 mg EV protein per kg body weight (Fig. 1A). A similar trend was also seen in studies utilising particle number as an EV dose quantification. In addition, the rationale for EV dose selection and treatment frequency is largely lacking in the analysed pre-clinical studies. For instance, the frequency of administration of EV-based therapeutics varied from 1 up to 6 times in studies targeting Experimental Autoimmune Encephalomyelitis (EAE) [83–88]. Importantly, segregation of the studies based on the route of administration showed a clear trend of using higher doses with systemic routes such as I.V or I.P over local delivery routes such as I.M.C., I.C.V. etc. irrespective of the disease model (Fig. 1B).

Furthermore, we questioned if the variation in EV dose across the studies is primarily due to differences in animal species. As higher animal species have lower metabolic rates and body surface area to weight ratio, large animal species often require lower doses to observe similar therapeutic effects [157]. Upon distributing the data set based on animal species used in the preclinical model, EV dosing inconsistency could still not be resolved. Still, importantly the median therapeutic dose for larger animal species was lower than smaller animals (Fig. 1C). Notably, current dose conversion factors are relatively simple empirical formulae without considering various physiological parameters and behaviour of drugs, applicability of these factors in EVs therapeutics must be taken with caution. Therefore, dose–response studies across multiple animal species preclinical models are invaluable for determining dose conversion factors for EV-based therapeutics. Yet, we noticed

a complete lack of studies conducting comprehensive assessments of dose–response kinetics *in vivo*.

Interestingly, the median therapeutic dose in studies using direct isolation methods such as precipitation or ultrafiltration was approximately ten times lower than studies using EV purification methods based on size or density (Fig. 1D and E). As mentioned before, the techniques used for EV purification can drastically affect the total protein amount in the final preparation. The propensity of methods based on precipitation or ultrafiltration to co-purify soluble proteins is higher than purification systems that separate EVs based on size or density, especially when producer cells are cultured in serum-supplemented conditions [13]. This hence leads to a reduction of the effective EVs dose in studies using total protein amount as a dose quantification in conjunction with direct isolation methods.

Furthermore, large variation in dosing existed also when evaluating the data set based on the target disease type, with the therapeutic dose for neurological diseases being lower than for systemic inflammatory diseases, even though only a fraction of EV dose has been shown to localise to the CNS after systemic administration (Fig. 1F) [4,89,90]. Notably, the majority of EV pharmacokinetics studies have been conducted in wild-type (WT) animal models. However, EV distribution can differ dramatically in a diseased animal, primarily due to the unique ability of EVs to home into a target diseased organ, which may explain the observed therapeutic benefits at lower therapeutic doses in disease models [91].

This inconsistency in the dosing range highlights the limitation associated with current EV quantification tools. The majority of

Table 2
Summary of dosing strategy of selected preclinical studies targeting neurological diseases using EV-based therapeutics.

Disease model	Animal	Route of injection	Dosing scheme	Purification	Therapeutic cargo	Cell source	Ref
EAE	Mouse	I.V	3 injections of 1×10^{10} particles in PBS either on day 1, 4 and 7p.d.i (prophylactic treatment) or day 11, 14 and 17p.d.i (therapeutic treatment)	UC	Native	mOligodendrocyte's progenitor cells (SF)	[87]
EAE	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 40 μ g EV protein in PBS on day 15p.d.i	UC	Native	mSerum	[88]
EAE	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 24 μ g EV protein in PBS on day 14p.d.i	Exoquick	Native	hPeriodontal ligament stem cells (SF)	[83]
EAE	Mouse	Intranasal	Intranasal administration of 1.5 nmol curcumin encapsulated in EVs in PBS daily for 26 days p.d.i	Density gradient centrifugation	Exogenously loaded with curcumin by incubation	mEL-4 lymphoma cells (EV depleted serum)	[84]
EAE	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 150 μ g EV protein in PBS at the peak of the disease	UC	Native	IFN gamma stimulated hBM-MSC (EV depleted serum)	[85]
EAE	Mouse	I.V	6 injections of 5×10^9 particles in PBS on day 1, 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11p.d.i	UF-SEC	Endogenously engineered for displaying cytokine decoy receptors	hBM-MSC (SF)	[86]
TBI	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 30 μ g EV protein in PBS at 1 h p.d.i	Anion exchange chromatography	Native	hBM-MSC (SF)	[116]
TBI	Rat	I.V	3 injections of 1×10^{10} Particles in PBS at 4–6 h, 24–26 h and 48–50 h p.d.i	UF	Native	hESC derived Neural stem cells	[117]
TBI	Rat	I.V	1 injection of 100 μ g EV protein in PBS 1 day p.d.i	Exoquick	Native	rBM-MSC (EV depleted serum)	[118]
TBI	Mouse	Intra cerebral ventricular (I.C.V)	1 injection of 10 μ g EV protein at 1 h p.d.i	UC	Exogenously engineered with plasmid encoding Bcl2 and shRNA against Bax using Exofect	mAstrocytes (Serum)	[119]
Middle cerebral artery occlusion	Mouse	I.V	3 injections of EVs release by 2×10^6 cells in saline on day 0, 3 and 5p.d.i	PEG precipitation	Native	hBM-MSC (Serum)	[120]
WT	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 150 μ g EV protein in 5% glucose	UC	Endogenously engineered for the display of RVG peptide and exogenously loaded with siRNA against BACE1 using electroporation	mDC (EV depleted serum)	[121]
WT	Mouse	I.C.V	ICV infusion of 1 μ g of HTT siRNA loaded in $2-3 \times 10^{10}$ particles in PBS per day for 7 days using an osmotic pump	UC	Exogenously engineered with Cholesterol modified siRNA against Htt	U87 glioblastoma cell line (EV depleted serum)	[95]
Huntington Disease transgenic model	Mouse	I.C.V	1 ICV injection of EVs from 5 ml of Condition medium in PBS	Exoquick	Endogenously engineered by overexpression of miR-124 in producer cells	HEK293 (EV depleted serum)	[122]
Photothrombotic stroke model	NHP	I.V	2 injections of 3 mg/kg EV protein in PBS at 24 h and 48 h p.d.i	UC	Endogenously engineered for the display of RVG peptide and loaded with SCM11 circular RNA by overexpression in producer cells	HEK293T (Serum)	[123]
PD transgenic model	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 150 μ g EV protein in 5% glucose	UC	Endogenously engineered for display of RVG peptide and exogenously loaded with siRNA against alpha synuclein using electroporation	mDC (EV depleted serum)	[124]
PD	Mouse	Intranasal	Administration of 1.2×10^9 particles in PBS every other day for two weeks	UC	Exogenously loaded with catalase enzyme	RAW 264.7 (Serum)	[125]
PD	Mouse	I.V	10 injections of dopamine loaded EVs (dopamine dose equivalent to levodopa 4.95 mg/kg) in PBS at an interval of 1 day	UC	Exogenously loaded with dopamine	mSerum	[96]
Alzheimer's Disease	Mouse	I.V	4 injections of 30 μ g EV protein in PBS every 2 weeks	Exoquick	Native	hUmbilical cord-MSC (SF)	[126]
Cerebral Ischemia	Mouse	I.V	I.V administration of 300 μ g EV protein in PBS at 12 h p.d.i	Density gradient centrifugation	Exogenously engineered with c (RGDyK) targeting peptide and electroporated with curcumin	mBM-MSC (EV depleted serum)	[127]

Traumatic brain injury (TBI); Parkinson disease (PD); Dendritic Cells (DC).

Table 3
Summary of dosing strategy of selected preclinical studies targeting cancer using EV-based therapeutics.

Disease model	Animal	Route of injection	Dosing scheme	Purification	Therapeutic cargo	Cell source	Ref
AML Xenograft	Mouse	I.P	5 injections of 3.3×10^{12} particles in PBS every other day for 9 days	UC	Exogenously loaded with miR-125b ASOs	hRBC (Calcium ionophore)	[128]
Glioma	Mouse	I.V	Injection of 1×10^{12} particles in PBS every 3 days until the end of the study	UC	Endogenously loaded with PTEN mRNA	MEF (SF)	[129]
Pancreatic cancer	Mouse	I.P	Injection of 1×10^8 particles every other day in PBS until the end of the study	UC	Exogenously loaded with siRNA against KRAS	hBJ fibroblast (EV depleted serum)	[130]
Myeloma	Mouse	Subcutaneous	Injection of 30 μ g EV protein in PBS 6 days prior to tumour cells inoculation	UC	Endogenously engineered with HSPs	J558 myeloma cells (Heat shock + SF)	[131]
Melanoma	Mouse	I.T	4 injections of 200 μ g EV protein in PBS every 48 h on day 35 post tumour inoculation	UC	Endogenously engineered with TRAIL	K562 (SF)	[132]
Lymphoma	Mouse	I.V	4 injections of 600 μ g EV protein in PBS every 48 h	UC	Endogenously engineered with TRAIL	K562 (SF)	[132]
Colon colorectal	Mouse	I.T or I.V	5 I.T injections of 100 μ g exosomes or 5 I.V injections of 200 μ g in PBS every 72 h	UC	Endogenously engineered for displaying SIRP alpha	HEK293T (SF)	[133]
Breast cancer	Mouse	I.V	6 injections of 3 mg/kg Dox encapsulated in EVs every 72 h from day 3 to day 21	Density gradient UC	Endogenously engineered to display iRGD peptide and electroporate with doxorubicin	Immature mDC (Serum)	[97]
Colon carcinoma	Mouse	I.T	3 injections of 100 ng of IL-12 protein displayed on EVs surface in PBS, on day 6, 8, and 10 post tumour inoculation	UC	Endogenously engineered to display IL-12	HEK293T (SF)	[98]
Melanoma	Mouse	I.T	8 injections of 100 ng of IL-12 protein displayed on EVs surface in PBS, every 48 h on day 4 post tumour inoculation	UC	Endogenously engineered to display IL-12	HEK293T (SF)	[98]
Chronic Myelogenous Leukaemia	Mouse	I.P	2 I.P injections per week for three weeks of 10 μ g of EV protein in PBS, 7 days p.d.i	UC	Endogenously engineered with IL3-Lamp2B and siRNA against BCR-ABL	HEK293T (EV depleted serum)	[134]

Intraperitoneal (I.P); Intra tumour (I.T)

currently used means for EV quantification provide only an approximation of actual numbers and fail to address the disparities introduced at every step of production. Therefore, alternative ways of quantification for EV dosing are needed, which can account for the variety of distinctive factors coming with different means of therapeutic EV production. The primary hurdle in robust EV quantification is addressing the EVs in their full complexity. EVs are a multicomponent entity comprising more than 1000 proteins and an intricate array of nucleic acids [3]. Furthermore, as EVs are a pool of heterogeneous particles, much focus has been applied on achieving single vesicle quantification [92]. However, these methods are still under development, and due to the inability to purify specific subpopulations, their functional or therapeutic relevance cannot be addressed yet. Therefore, instead of performing quantitative analysis, qualitative aspects should be in the focus of EV-based therapeutics, such as the establishment of EV potency assays. Considering this, various *in vitro* potency assays have been developed, for example, to measure the anti-inflammatory effect of EVs by analysing a specific cytokine secretion signature or changes in physiological processes in recipient cells [93]. Thus, an EV potency unit could be a viable tool to standardise EV dosing, however, these assays address only one qualitative aspect so far. Another EV dose standardisation technique is based on the quantity of effector molecules. Most of the studies utilising engineered EVs use the quantification of the effector molecule, for instance, a protein or miRNA present in the EVs, which is responsible for the therapeutic outcome. This strategy is promising to help reduce the batch-to-batch variation during EV production as well as the difference in cell source or culture conditions. This quantification method will also allow for the successful benchmarking of EV-based therapeutics compared to other nanoparticle drug delivery

systems. The applicability of this strategy has been shown in various studies where either EV dosing was based on the amount of small molecule or siRNA, respectively, loaded inside the EVs, or the amount of engineered protein displayed on their surface or loaded into the EV lumen [84,94–98]. For instance, Lewis et al. used the amount of IL-12 displayed on the surface of engineered EVs as a dose quantification in a pre-clinical model of melanoma [98]. Similarly, Qu et al. dosed the engineered EVs in PD models based on the amount of dopamine loaded inside the EVs [96].

In comparison, an analogous strategy is utilised across the drug delivery field using other delivery vectors such as Adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) and Lentiviruses (LVs), where the dose for both clinical and pre-clinical *in vivo* applications is based on the encapsulated biotherapeutic agent instead of the delivery vector amount. However, for *ex vivo* applications, dosing is based on viral potency units [99,100,158]. The primary reason for this ensues from the fact that a large proportion of the viral particles is empty, thus introducing a potential quantification bias [101]. Similar strategies are used in the synthetic nanoparticle field, where lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) encapsulated with mRNA or siRNA are clinically dosed based on cargo amount and not nanoparticle quantity [102,103]. Similar limitations are also associated with EV-based therapeutics primarily due to the fact that EVs are cell-derived products, and various physiological parameters from cell passage to transcriptomic changes of the cell during culture can variably affect each EV preparation. Thus, for a successful clinical transition of EV-based therapeutics, qualitative dosing methods will aid in further innovation by achieving reproducibility.

Despite a steadily increasing amount of outstanding data being published on EVs, the field is still only in its infancy. To date, we

Table 4
Summary of dosing strategy of selected preclinical studies targeting systemic diseases using EV-based therapeutics.

Disease model	Animal	Route of injection	Dosing scheme	Purification	Therapeutic cargo	Cell source	Ref
CLP induced Sepsis	Mouse	I.P	4 injections of 1×10^9 particles in PBS at 0, 6, 12 and 18 h p.d.i	UF-SEC	Endogenously engineered for loading super-repressor IκB	HEK293T (EV depleted serum)	[135]
LPS induced Sepsis	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 200 μg EV protein in PBS immediately p.d.i	UC	Native	mAdipose tissue derived stem cells (Serum)	[136]
LPS induced Sepsis	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 5×10^9 particles in saline immediately p.d.i	Anion Exchange chromatography	Native	hMSC (SF)	[137]
CLP induced Sepsis	Rat	I.V	1 injection of 100 μg EV protein in saline at 3 h p.d.i	UC	Native	rAdipose derived-MSC (Serum)	[138]
LPS induced acute lung inflammation	Mouse	I.V	2 injections of 3 mg/kg piceatannol loaded in EVs in HBSS at 4 and 8 h p.d.i	UC	Exogenous loading of piceatannol using pH gradient	HL-60 hNeutrophil cell line (SF)	[94]
LPS induced Sepsis	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 1×10^{11} particles in PBS at 3 h p.d.i	UF-SEC	Endogenously engineered for displaying cytokine decoy receptors	hBM-MSC (SF)	[86]
CCL4 induced mouse Liver fibrosis	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 200 μg EV protein in PBS at 24 h after CCL4 injection (Repeated 8 times over 4 weeks)	Exoquick	Endogenously engineered for loading HuR RNA binding protein into EVs	HEK293T (SF)	[139]
LPS induced acute lung inflammation	Mouse	Intratracheal	1 injection of 15 μg EV protein in PBS at 2 h p.d.i.	exoEasy	Endogenously engineered for the display of Rage binding peptides and Exogenously loaded with curcumin using electroporation	HEK293T (EV depleted serum)	[140]
Influenza induced acute lung injury	Pig	Intratracheal	1 injection of 80 μg/kg EV protein in PBS at 12 h p.d.i	UC	Native	Pig BM-MSC (SF)	[141]
DSS induced colitis	Mouse	I.V	3 injections of 400 μg EV protein in PBS at day 3, 6 and 9p.d.i	UF-Density gradient centrifugation	Native	hUmbilical cord-MSC (SF)	[142]
Ulcerative colitis	Mouse	Oral gavage	4 oral administrations of 200 μg EV protein in PBS on day 0, 1, 2 and 3p.d.i	UC	Native	Cow Milk	[143]
DSS induced colitis	Mouse	I.P	1 injection of 200 μg EV protein in PBS on day 1p.d.i	UC	Native	hUmbilical cord-MSC (SF)	[144]
TNBS induced colitis	Rat	I.P	1 injection of 10 μg EV protein in PBS on day 3p.d.i	UC	Native	IL-10 treated rDC (EV depleted serum)	[145]
TNBS induced colitis	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 3×10^{11} particles in PBS on day 1p.d.i	UF-SEC	Endogenously engineered for displaying cytokine decoy receptors	hBM-MSC	[86]
DSS induced colitis	Mouse	I.P	6 injections of 50 μg EV protein in PBS on day 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6p.d.i	Exosome extraction kit	Native	mDC treated with Schistosoma japonicum (Serum)	[146]
DSS induced colitis	Mouse	I.P	8 injections of 50 mg/kg (=90–100 μg EV protein) in PBS from day 1 to day 8p.d.i	Exosome isolation kit	Native	mMacrophages (Serum)	[147]
DSS induced colitis	Mouse	I.P	3 injections of 100 μg EV protein in PBS on day 1, 3, and 5p.d.i	UC	Native	Canine Adipose tissue- MSCs (EV depleted serum)	[148]
Chronic GVHD	Mouse	I.V	6 injections of 100 μg EV protein in PBS each from day 22p.d.i onwards once per week for 6 weeks.	UC	Native	Canine Adipose tissue-MSC (EV depleted serum)	[149]
GVHD	Mouse	I.V	10 μg EV protein in PBS injection every 3rd day from day 1 to day 34p.d.i	UF	Native	hESC-MSC (SF)	[150]
Acute GVHD	Mouse	I.V	1 injection of 1.6×10^7 particles/16 μg protein in saline on day 5p.d.i	Total exosome Isolation kit	Native	hBM-MSC (SF)	[151]

Cecal ligation and puncture (CLP); Lipopolysachride (LPS); Trinitrobenzenesulfonic acid (TNBS); Dextran sulfate sodium (DSS); Graft vs host disease (GVHD).

Fig. 1. A) Graphical representation of identified EV doses based on protein or particle quantification across 50 different preclinical studies. B) Segregation of EV doses used in different studies based on the route of administration. C) Distribution of EV dosing used in preclinical studies based on the species of the animal model used. Effect of EV purification method used in the preclinical studies on EV dosing based on D) Number of particles and E) Total protein amount. F) Representation of EV doses used in the preclinical studies as therapeutic intervention based upon the target disease type.

Table 5
Summary of ongoing clinical trials utilising EVs as a therapeutic intervention.

Disease	Dosing scheme	Route of administration	Therapeutic cargo	Cell source	Ref
Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome	2.0×10^8 – 1.6×10^9 particles every day for 7 days	Inhalation	Native	hMSC	NCT04602104
Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia	200 pmol phospholipid/kg	I.V	Native	hBM-MSC	NCT03857841
Pulmonary infection	8.0×10^8 – 1.6×10^9 particles every day for 7 days	Inhalation	Native	hAdipose tissue-MSC	NCT04544215
Covid-19	2×10^8 particles every day from day 1 to day 5.	Inhalation	Native	COVID-19 Specific hT Cell	NCT04389385
Dry Eye	10 µg/drop, four times a day for 14 days.	Eye drops	Native	hUmbilical cord-MSCs	NCT04213248
Covid-19	1×10^{10} particles	Inhalation	CD24	HEK 293 T	NCT04747574
Multiple Organ Failure	150 mg EV protein once a day for 14 times	I.V	Native	hMSC	NCT04356300
Macular Holes	50 µg or 20 µg EV protein	Eye drop	Native	hUmbilical cord-MSCs	NCT03437759
Covid-19	0.5 – 2×10^{10} of particle	Inhalation	Native	hMSC	NCT04602442
Alzheimer Disease	5–20 µg EV protein twice a week for 12 weeks	Nasal drip	Native	hAdipose tissue-MSC	NCT04388982
Covid-19	3 injections of 8×10^9 particles every other day	I.V	Native	hMSC	NCT04798716

have successfully overcome many, although by far not all, hurdles in reproducibly producing therapeutically active EVs, and their promising effects warrant the excitement the field has gained in recent years [1,3,159]. As a result of the all the promising work in various pre-clinical models, several clinical trials are currently assessing the regenerative potential of EVs in numerous acute diseases. Also, EVs are currently utilised as a next-generation delivery vector in clinical trials for tissue-specific delivery of biotherapeutics. To date, more than 27 clinical trials are on-going, with the majority focusing on an intervention for Covid-19 associated acute respiratory distress syndrome (Table 5). Overall, the dose determination in the ongoing clinical trials has been based on EV particle numbers, and since most of the studies are using local administration routes, comparison with pre-clinical studies is difficult. Furthermore, a reliable road map is much needed to extrapolate the EV dose for patients from preclinical models, since EVs have the unique ability to achieve body-wide tissue distribution and exhibit a non-linear pharmacokinetic profile in plasma. Applying current dose conversion factors across the species can lead to variable outcomes as observed using PEGylated liposomes, where the converted dose from animal models to humans varied by 30% [160]. Another layer of complexity is added by the heterogeneous composition of EV populations. Therefore, better knowledge and awareness of EV heterogeneity as well as a deeper understanding of pathways involved in EV uptake *in vivo* is required to reliably predict effects of EV-based therapeutics in humans.

Moreover, since EVs are a cell-derived material, differences in species of the EV origin to the target animal model, can have significant implications *in vivo*. Therefore, future emphasis should be laid on investigating pharmacokinetic and toxicity profiles of different EV populations in a range of species. Overall, these facts highlight that new allosteric dose conversion factors need to be established for EVs to determine non-toxic and efficacious doses for phase I clinical trials.

5. Summary

Over the past decade, various reports have shown the tremendous therapeutic potential of EVs in numerous diseases. This is also clearly implied by the increasing number of clinical trials utilising EVs as a therapeutic intervention. Despite major development in modifying EVs for therapeutic use, the field of EV-based therapeutics has faced hurdles in manufacturing, purification, and characterisation. In the present literature analysis, we could visualize substantial variations in EV purification and characterisation underlying therapeutic dosing strategies. Although these strongly

contribute to the current lack of robustness between studies, the potential clinical application of EVs has opened an exciting new avenue for the effective delivery of therapeutics. With the increasing interest in the field, harmonised assays and standard operating procedures need to be established in order to decrease the discrepancies between studies. The majority of the shortcomings can be addressed by adapting qualitative quantification, similar to the techniques used in the nanoparticle drug delivery field. In addition, efforts directed towards developing *in vitro* potency assays for standardising each EV batch irrespective of cell source and choice of purification will contribute significantly to the field of EV-based therapeutics.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by the European Union H2020 EXPERT grant as well as the Swedish Foundation of Strategic Research (SSF-IRC, FormulaEx).

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